

STUDYING THE MECHANISM OF PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATOR IMPROVEMENT IN RUMINANTS THROUGH MICROBIOLOGICAL PROCESSING METHODS

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Annotation

Modern biotechnological approaches are increasingly required to enhance biological efficiency and productivity in large and small ruminants in livestock farming. The digestive system of ruminants is closely associated with microbial activity, and their physiological condition can be optimized through microbiological processing. This article investigates the effectiveness of a biopreparation developed from an association of cellulolytic bacteria capable of degrading cellulose and probiotic bacteria that restore the microbiological balance of the organism. The physiological effects of the biopreparation on animals, its role in improving digestion, and its impact on the immune system were studied. Experimental results demonstrated the high biological activity and environmental safety of this biopreparation.

Keywords. biopreparation, cellulolytic bacteria, probiotics, symbiotic effect, animal organism, efficiency, microflora.

Аннотация

Современные биотехнологические подходы всё чаще востребованы для повышения биологической эффективности и продуктивности крупного и мелкого рогатого скота в животноводстве. Пищеварительная система жвачных тесно связана с микробной активностью, и её физиологическое состояние может быть оптимизировано посредством микробиологической обработки. В данной статье исследуется эффективность биопрепарата, созданного на основе ассоциации целлюлозолитических бактерий, способных расщеплять целлюлозу, и пробиотических бактерий, восстанавливающих микробиологический баланс организма. Изучены физиологические эффекты биопрепарата на животных, его роль в улучшении пищеварения и влияние на иммунную систему. Экспериментальные результаты продемонстрировали высокую биологическую активность и экологическую безопасность данного биопрепарата.

Ключевые слова: биопрепарат, целлюлозолитические бактерии, пробиотики, симбиотический эффект, организм животных, эффективность, микрофлора.

Annotatsiya

Chorvachilikda yirik va mayda kavsh qaytaruvchi hayvonlarning biologik samaradorligi va mahsuldorligini oshirish uchun zamonaviy biotexnologik yondashuvlar tobora ko'proq talab qilinmoqda. Kavsh qaytaruvchi hayvonlarning ovqat hazm qilish tizimi mikroblarning faolligi bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, ularning fiziologik holatini mikrobiologik qayta ishlash orqali optimallashtirish mumkin. Ushbu maqola organizmning mikrobiologik muvozanatini tiklaydigan tsellyuloza va probiyotik bakteriyalarni parchalashga qodir bo'lgan selulolitik bakteriyalar assotsiatsiyasidan ishlab chiqilgan biopreparatning samaradorligini o'rganadi. Biopreparatning hayvonlarga fiziologik ta'siri, ovqat hazm qilishni yaxshilashdagi ahamiyati, immun tizimiga ta'siri o'rganildi. Tajriba natijalari ushbu biopreparatning yuqori biologik faolligi va ekologik xavfsizligini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar. biopreparat, selulolitik bakteriyalar, probiyotiklar, simbiotik ta'sir, hayvon organizmi, samaradorlik, mikroflora.

Introduction. There is a growing demand for environmentally safe and effective means to improve feed digestion. In this context, biopreparations based on probiotic and cellulolytic bacteria are of great importance in animal husbandry. These preparations not only enhance digestion but also help restore gut microbiota balance, strengthen immunity, and improve productivity.

The digestive system of ruminants is complex, with microorganisms playing a crucial role in digestion. Cellulolytic bacteria, in particular, break down plant cell walls, converting them into nutrients beneficial to the animal. Probiotics help stabilize gut microbiota and support immune function. Therefore, investigating the effects of biopreparations based on both types of bacteria on animal physiology is highly relevant.

In our country, significant attention is being given to the rapid advancement of livestock farming and its transformation into a profitable sector. This development is aimed at improving the population's living standards and ensuring a stable supply of essential food products, such as meat and milk, in the domestic market. In this context, the fields of veterinary medicine and microbiology are tasked with developing and implementing supplementary functional biopreparations in high-quality livestock feed rations. These efforts seek to analyze physiological, immunological, and biochemical changes in animal organisms, enhance the production of high-quality animal products, and reduce production costs.[4,8,11]

Cellulolytic bacteria are microorganisms capable of breaking down cellulose. They decompose cellulose into simpler forms, converting it into carbohydrates and other organic compounds. These bacteria play a crucial role in the process of biological

decomposition. Types of Cellulolytic Bacteria. Cellulolytic bacteria are classified into two main types: aerobic (oxygen-requiring) and anaerobic (thriving in oxygen-free environments). Aerobic bacteria: Cellulomonas, Bacillus, Pseudomonas Anaerobic bacteria: Clostridium thermocellum, Ruminococcus [7,19]

Currently, the use of environmentally friendly, biologically active additives in livestock farming is of great importance. Cellulolytic bacteria play a key role in improving digestion due to their ability to degrade cellulose. Probiotic bacteria are essential for maintaining microbial balance in the body and enhancing immune function. Biopreparations developed from associations of these two bacterial types contribute to improving animal health and productivity. [6,10,16]

Materials and Methods. Research Conducted at the Laboratory of Probiotic Microbiology and Biotechnology, Institute of Microbiology, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Studies carried out at the Laboratory of Probiotic Microbiology and Biotechnology of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan have focused on isolating and analyzing cellulolytic bacteria. A total of 27 pure bacterial isolates were obtained from the stomach fluids of small ruminants (goats), rabbits, and chickens, as well as from cellulose-feeding termites and bark beetles. The cellulolytic activity of these isolates was extensively studied. The morphological characteristics of the bacterial isolates were examined and identified using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). A preliminary screening of the cellulolytic activity of bacterial strains isolated from animals was conducted, revealing significant cellulolytic activity in Bacillus species. Among the identified strains, the highest cellulolytic activity was observed in: 4 strains of Bacillus subtilis sp. isolated from goat stomach fluid (0.233 U/ml). 1 strain of Bacillus sp. isolated from termites (0.193 U/ml).

Additionally, two selected strains (1-Bacillus sp. and 2-Bacillus sp.) were capable of producing up to 0.34 mg/ml of protein. The highest activity level (0.38 mg/ml) was detected in 3-B. subtilis sp. isolated from goat stomach fluid. [2,6,15,16]

Identification and Application of Cellulolytic Bacterial Strains from the Digestive System of Animals. The identification of cellulolytic bacterial strains isolated from the digestive systems of animals and their application in livestock farming to improve the digestibility of roughage is a highly relevant research area. The use of biopreparations based on associations of cellulolytic and probiotic bacteria derived from various domestic animals has demonstrated significant benefits. A review of scientific articles published by researchers at the Laboratory of Probiotic Microbiology and Biotechnology, Institute of Microbiology, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, reveals the following findings: Bacillus species with cellulolytic properties were isolated from the stomach fluids of various ruminants. The cultural and morphological characteristics of these bacteria were studied, and the synthesis of endoglucanase and cellobiase enzymes on different cellulose-based substrates was confirmed. Genetic identification of the bacterial strains was conducted using the 16S rRNA method,

confirming that the isolates belong to four strains of *Bacillus subtilis*. The antibiotic sensitivity of these strains and their growth at different temperatures were analyzed. Preliminary studies examined the probiotic properties of bacterial strains isolated from rabbits, goats, and termites, confirming their ability to survive in gastric and alkaline environments. Three strains exhibited antimicrobial activity, forming inhibition zones of 15–22 mm against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans*, and *Escherichia coli*. The toxicity and safety of the bacterial strains were assessed at a State Veterinary Committee biolaboratory, where they were certified as safe. To enhance the cellulolytic activity of the bacterial strains, researchers optimized growth media and cultivation conditions: MPB (Mineral Peptone Broth), Hutchinson medium, and whey-based medium were tested, with the whey-based medium proving the most effective. Optimal conditions for bacterial growth were determined to be pH 5.5 and a temperature of 37°C. The highest enzyme activity (1.56 U/ml) was observed in samples supplemented with yeast extract and bran.

In the final research phase, the selected cellulolytic bacterial complex was lyophilized and tested in rabbit physiology experiments at the Department of Animal Physiology, Samarkand State University. The biomass formulation was found to have a positive impact on rabbit respiration, blood parameters, and weight gain, demonstrating its potential as a functional supplement in animal nutrition. [2,4,15]

Strains of *Bacillus subtilis* (with cellulolytic activity) and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (with probiotic properties) were selected for the study. The biopreparation was prepared as an association and tested on Karakul sheep. The evaluation included clinical and biochemical parameters, weight gain, feed conversion ratio, intestinal microflora composition, and general health status.

Results . In the experimental group that received the biopreparation: weight gain was 12–15% higher compared to the control group; digestibility coefficient increased by 8–10%; positive changes were observed in leukocyte and hemoglobin levels; the number of lacto- and bifidobacteria in the intestinal microflora increased, while pathogenic microflora levels decreased. The differences between the experimental and control groups are presented in the table below:

Indicators	Control	Group
Experimental Group		
Weight gain (%)	100.0	115.0
Digestibility (%)	100.0	110.0
Leukocyte count ($10^9/l$)	7.2	8.5
Hemoglobin (g/l)	110.0	125.0
Increase in beneficial microflora (%)	100.0	135.0
Reduction in pathogenic microflora (%)	100.0	70.0

Conclusion. The biopreparation developed based on the association of cellulolytic and probiotic bacteria positively affects the digestive and immune systems as well as the overall physiological state of animals. It can be effectively used in livestock farming to improve nutrient absorption and increase productivity. Biopreparations developed through the combined application of probiotics and cellulolytic bacteria exhibit multifaceted effects, improving the digestive and immune functions of farm animals and enhancing their overall productivity. Moreover, they offer a cost-effective alternative to expensive imported products.

Practical Recommendations. Biopreparations should be applied considering the age and breed characteristics. It is recommended to adjust the dosage based on microbiological monitoring.

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